

Human Tracking across Heterogeneous Systems Based on Mobile Agent Technologies

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Abstract : In a human tracking system, expanding a monitoring range of one system is complicating the management of devices and increasing its cost. Therefore, we propose a method to realize a wide-range human tracking by connecting small systems. In this paper, we examined an agent deploy method and information contents across the heterogeneous human tracking systems. By implementing the proposed method, we can construct a human tracking system across heterogeneous systems, and the system can track a target continuously between systems.

Keywords : human tracking system, mobile agent, monitoring, heterogeneous systems

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